

Influential Factors on Job Burnout among China's Nursing College Faculties: The Mediating Role of Psychological Capital

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Abstract

Background: Compared to other professions, nursing teachers in Chinese nursing universities face a more complex role as teachers, clinical practitioners, and family responsibilities with a high potential for stress.

Objectives: This study aimed to uncover the trial roles that influence job burnout and the function of psychological variables as a mediating variable in the relationship between the two variables. It also investigated the significant role of psychological capital as a mediating variable.

Methods: This study employed a survey and interview design. First, three questionnaires, MBI-S, PsyCap, and WMC, were administered to 200 nursing teachers from different regions in China. Then, semi-structured interviews were conducted with six respondents based on their teaching experience and academic rank.

Result: The regression analysis indicated that conflict among work-family and family-work relations positively influenced job burnout. Psychological capital (PsyCap) played a dual role as a mediating variable when it dealt with emotional exhaustion and cynicism and a moderating variable when it dealt with professional efficacy. The finding also indicated that age and teaching experience positively correlated with job burnout.

Conclusion: This study underscores the significant strain that nursing educators in Chinese universities experience due to their multifaceted responsibilities, which include teaching, clinical practice, and family responsibilities. The interplay of these role conflicts influences the variables of work-family and family-work relationships. Then, job fatigue significantly impacts participants' emotional exhaustion and cynicism. Psychological capital (PsyCap) has emerged

as a critical mediating factor, reducing the impact of role conflict on emotional exhaustion and cynicism while also acting as a moderating factor that enhances professional efficacy.

Unique contribution: Understanding the dual function of psychological capital in role conflict and job burnout is crucial in nursing education, as it serves as a mediator and moderator, addressing specific burnout dimensions.

Key recommendation: Professional development programmes should be tailored to cater for the needs of teachers of all ages and experience levels to enhance their stress management.

Keywords: Educator burnout, clinical practice, family interference, trial-role conflict, emotional exhaustion

Introduction

Burnout is characterised as a symptom of diminished professional performance and emotional weariness (Bodenheimer & Shuster, 2020). It commonly occurs among people with double or triple roles, such as in nursing or another health field (Lee, 2019). In the academic world, especially among lecturers at nursing colleges in China, job burnout is a significant concern that impacts not only individual well-being but also educational and health services. The pressure has created a stressful environment for teachers. On a personal level, instructors face challenges such as misconduct among students, lack of autonomy, feelings of separation, and the added stress of balancing home and work responsibilities. These factors can significantly contribute to the burnout feeling of the teacher (Bodenheimer & Shuster, 2020; Lee, 2019).

Job fatigue has been the subject of numerous studies in various professions, including the healthcare sector (Li & Zhang, 2018; Wu et al., 2021). Insights into the management of dual duties of work and family by health workers are provided by the studies, which may have an impact on job burnout. Nevertheless, these investigations are distinct from the job fatigue observed in Chinese nursing colleges. In Chinese nursing colleges, educators are responsible for various responsibilities that incorporate health and education. These responsibilities include clinical practice, supervision, research, and health services.

Furthermore, teachers at nursing faculties in China face both dual-career and trial-career; they must balance their duties as teachers, clinical practice, and family roles (Wu et al., 2021). Those in the education profession with families face significant emotional and physical challenges as they attempt to balance academic responsibilities, clinical responsibilities, and family commitments. This could result in increased stress and burnout, exacerbating the challenges associated with their dual duties as educators and family members. Exploring the factors contributing to job burnout among teachers in Chinese nursing colleges is essential for understanding the dynamics of educational institutions and the work environment. This scenario enables educators to sustain an equilibrium between their responsibilities in nursing colleges and familial obligations. This study investigates the impact of trial roles among Chinese nursing educators on job burnout, with Psychological Capital serving as a mediating variable.

Literature Review

Psychological Capital (PsyCap) in Education

PsyCap refers to the psychological condition of individuals, characterised by four essential traits (Luthans et al., 2019). Initially, it encompasses assurance and a person's conviction to address intricate challenges effectively. Secondly, it involves maintaining a positive outlook on current and upcoming accomplishments. Thirdly, it showcases persistence and resolve to achieve objectives (hope) while maintaining the adaptability to modify approaches when needed. Ultimately, it involves sustaining resilience when confronted with challenges to attain success. Luthans et al. (2019) identify four distinct elements that comprise PsyCap: optimism, efficacy, hope, and resilience.

Meanwhile, the definition of hope is a constructive mindset that emerges from a feeling of accomplished control over one's actions (focused on goal energy) and pathways (thinking to achieve goals) that are obtained from interaction (Snyder, 1994). Self-efficacy is self-belief and confidence in one's ability to effectively carry out a specific activity within a particular situation by utilising one's motivation, cognitive abilities, and appropriate actions (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). Resilience is the individual condition to swiftly recover from challenges, conflicts, setbacks, favourable events, advancements, and increased obligations (Luthans et al., 2019). Resilience is returning to a state of 'normalcy' following a hardship or setback and attaining elevated levels of strength and personal development (Luthans et al., 2019).

Trial role conflict: teaching-clinical practice-family and job burnout

Trial role conflict pertains to individuals' challenges and tensions when juggling multiple roles or tasks that require their time, attention, and energy. Within healthcare education, especially among nurses and other healthcare professionals, trial role conflict commonly entails managing many tasks associated with teaching, clinical practice, and family responsibilities sequentially (Singh et al., 2020). Teaching Role: Healthcare teachers are responsible for providing excellent student learning experiences, constructing curricula, administering exams, and keeping up with professional advancements (Li & Zhang, 2018). This position requires allocating time for curriculum design, assessment, student assistance, and continuous professional growth to ensure effective instructional strategies.

The clinical roles of healthcare educators incorporate clinical practice responsibilities and guide students in their clinical practice (Singh et al., 2020). The management of clinical practice and instructional responsibilities presents various challenges, necessitating that educators navigate patient care responsibilities, timetables, and ongoing professional development. Family Role: Healthcare teachers, in addition to their professional responsibilities, also have individual, familial duties that demand their attention (Singh et al., 2020). Family roles encompass many responsibilities, such as raising children, caring for older family members, overseeing domestic tasks, and engaging in communal activities. The interplay between professional and familial responsibilities frequently increases tension due to the limited time available (Singh et al., 2020). From the review of literature regarding the relationships between trial-role conflict and teachers' burnout, the hypothesis is formulated into:

H1: Trial-role conflict significantly influences job burnout among nursing Chinese college teachers in China.

The relationships among academic psychological capital, trial role conflict, and job burnout

The relationship between academic psychological capital, trial role conflict, and job burnout in the teaching profession is intricate and noteworthy (Luthans et al., 2019). The components of psychological capital, including self-efficacy, resilience, hope, and optimism, serve as vital indicators in assisting educators in navigating the challenges associated with trial-role conflict (Luthans et al., 2019). Educators with elevated psychological capital often demonstrate greater proficiency in balancing their teaching responsibilities, clinical practice, and family commitments. Educators are at a heightened risk of experiencing job fatigue when they encounter significant levels of trial role conflict in the absence of essential psychological factors, such as self-efficacy and resilience. Emotional fatigue, diminished job satisfaction, and a sense of overwhelm are all factors that contribute to burnout, which can be the result of balancing conflicting responsibilities (Jennings., 2020). Consequently, cultivating academic psychological capital can function as a protective measure, enabling educators to reduce the

likelihood of exhaustion and effectively manage the stress associated with their diverse responsibilities (Jennings, 2020). From the review of literature regarding the relationships between PsyCap as the mediating role of the trial role and teachers' burnout, the hypothesis is formulated into:

H2: Psychological capital (PsyCap) variable mediates the relationship between trial-role conflict and Chinese nursing college teachers' job burnout.

Research Methodology

Research Design

In order to improve the understanding of a research problem, this investigation implemented a sequential mixed-methods approach that included an interview and survey. Initially, the author collected and analysed survey data. Subsequently, a semi-structured interview was conducted to acquire qualitative insights. As suggested by Creswell (2021), a sequential approach could commence with a quantitative survey to identify general patterns, which would be followed by interviews designed to delve deeply into those patterns. The sequential mixed-method approach effectively leveraged the strengths of both survey and interview techniques, facilitating a more profound comprehension of intricate research questions.

Participants

The author utilised a stratified random sampling technique to guarantee an accurate sample representation of the research population. This method entails categorising the population into several strata depending on specific criteria, such as the size of the colleges, geographical location within Guizhou, the faculty members' or teachers' teaching experience, and academic rank. Eventually, 200 nursing teachers were selected from six Guizhou Province, Southwest China colleges.

Research Instrument and Data Collection

Questionnaire

a. Burnout Questionnaire

Maslach and Jackson established the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Survey (MBI-S) in 1981 to reflect burnout (Maslach & Jackson, 1981; Schaufeli et al., 1996). The MBI-S comprised 15 measures encompassing three parts: emotional cynicism, exhaustion, and professional efficacy. The author assessed the emotional exhaustion component using five measures, the cynicism dimension using four indicators, and the efficacy indicators involving six questions. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three indicators were 0.852, 0.912, and 0.896, respectively.

b. Academic Psychological Capital questionnaire

The Psychological Capital Questionnaire (PsyCap-Q), designed by (Luthans et al., 2019), is a highly popular tool for assessing PsyCap. This survey instrument involves two kinds: one with 24 items (PsyCap-Q-24) and another with 12 items (PsyCap-Q-12). This study derived the scales from well-established resilience, optimism, self-efficacy, and hope assessments. Validation studies provide evidence that PsyCap might be considered a second-order concept, as Luthans et al. (2019) suggested. Other languages have translated the 12-item version of the PsyCap-Q. The main objective of this inquiry is to justify the accuracy and consistency of a concise instrument for evaluating educational psychological capital (PsyCap). The Cronbach's alpha scale indicated 0.913.

c. Trial Role Conflict questionnaire

The author used the Work-Family Conflict Scale to assess role conflict in managing teaching, clinical practice, and familial responsibilities. This scale measured the degree to which individuals encounter conflicts between their employment (teaching and clinical practice) and home responsibilities. The author assessed the work-family variable using two subscales: the work-family (WF) scale and the family-work (FW) scale. The scale comprised 18 items, with nine assessing each of the two subscales. The current research found that the overall scale had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.897. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for work interference with Family (WIF) and family interference with work (FIW) were 0.914 and 0.886, respectively.

Semi-structured Interview

The author developed a semi-structured interview for the qualitative phase to facilitate in-depth discussions with participants. The interview items included open-ended questions related to experiences of burnout, how to balance the trial role (teaching-clinical practice-family), and which psychological dimensions (such as optimism, resilience, hope, and self-efficacy) had dominant roles in reducing job burnout and strengthening the trial role (teaching-clinical practice-family). Three senior teachers in the psychology and nursing fields validated the construction of the interview items. The author addressed suggestions and amendments based on their notes.

Data Analysis

The author employed a one-way ANOVA to analyse the aspects of burnout in different demographic categories and determine their respective distributions. The author used a Pearson correlation to check the association between trial-role conflict and burnout. The study employed the Luthans et al. (2019) approach to investigate the mediation function of PsyCap, work-family, and burnout variables. The author also employed the Sobel test to assess the statistical significance of the mediation effect. Finally, the author applied thematic analysis based on the burnout and PsyCap frameworks to analyse the semi-structured interview results, focusing on themes such as burnout experience, challenges, and efforts to balance the challenging role of teaching—clinical practice—and family roles.

Results

Table 1 displays the subjects' demographic and occupation data, as well as descriptions of every indicator of burnout variable. The average exhaustion, cynicism, emotion, and teacher efficacy levels varied among age categories. Next, Professional Efficacy varied among different academic rank groups. Among different teaching experience groups, there was a difference in average emotional exhaustion and average cynicism.

Table 1. Subject characteristics regarding demographics and occupation and burnout dimension in categorized items

Variable	Options	Per cent	Emotional exhaustion Mean	Cynicis m Mean	Professional efficacy Mean
Gender	Male	52	12.01	7.43	23.67
	Female	48	12.05	7.54	23.78
Age	Under 30 years old	32	13.28	8.29	24.99
	30-45 years old	52	12.07	8.43	25.21
	Over 45 years old	16	14.77	6.87	26.77

Academic Rank	Lecturer	45.5	14.27	7.52	24.92
	Assistant Professor	30	13.78	7.98	24.75
	Associate Professor	18	14.00	8.08	24.39
	Professor	6.5	13.97	8.11	25.09
Teaching Experience	Within five years	41.5	13.34	7.66	26.62
	6 to 10 years	30	12.83	8.31	24.61
	10-15 years	28.5	15.04	8.51	24.65
Marital Status	Single	24	14.91	8.27	23.38
	Married	70	15.70	8.88	25.19
	Divorced / widow	6	14.45	8.49	25.94

Correlations among trial-role conflict, Academic PsyCap, and burnout

Table 2 displays the Pearson correlation results—the correlation between trial-role conflict and the various characteristics of burnout. There was a positive correlation between WIF (work-family) and emotional exhaustion and between FIW (family-work) and cynicism. Nevertheless, the impacts of WIF (work-family) and FIW (family-work) on the professional efficacy dimension exhibited dissimilarities. Although FIW hurt professional Efficacy, WIF positively correlated with teacher effectiveness.

Table 2. Mean, Standard deviation, and correlation of variables

Variable	Mean	SD	Var 1	Var 2	Var 3	Var 4	Var 5	Var 6	Var 7
1. Teaching experience	9.6	2.78							
2. Age	37.45	8.01							
3. Emotional exhaustion	13.73	6.52	0.023	-					
4. Cynicism	8.63	6.45	0.117	-	0.790				
5. Professional Efficacy	24.39	8.78	0.075	0.068	0.115	0.212			
6. Trial role conflict (WIF)	4.31	0.65	0.016	0.215	0.356	-	-		
7. Trial role conflict (FIW)	2.74	0.73	0.231	0.102	0.234	0.345	-	-	
8. Academic PsyCap	4.25	0.53	-	0.137	-	-	0.302	0.428	
			0.113		0.267	0.435		0.154	0.168

The role of Academic PsyCap in the association between trial-role conflict and burnout dimension (emotional exhaustion).

The trial-role conflict dimensions among teachers, WIF and FIW, influence the dimension of burnout, especially emotional exhaustion (with score correlations of 0.476 and 0.213, respectively), while Academic PsyCap was negatively correlated (-0.215 and -0.236). Academic PsyCap partly mediated the association between WIF, FIW, and participants' emotional feelings, as the analysis results for FIW went down when PsyCap was included. For WIF, the coefficient decreased from 0.476 to 0.450 (see Table 3), while for FIW, the coefficient decreased from 0.213 to 0.167 (see Table 4).

Table 3. Dataset of hierarchical analysis for the trial-role conflict (WIF)

Variable	Job burnout					
	Emotional exhaustion		Cynicism		Professional Efficacy	
	First step	Second step	First step	Second step	First step	Second step
Gender	0.015	0.011	-0.012	-0.010	0.125	-0.002
Age	-0.065	-0.007	-0.091	-0.031	0.035	-0.013
Teaching experience	-0.014	-0.065	-0.069	-0.033	0.042	0.026
Marital status	0.140	0.092	0.074	0.020	0.004	0.030
WIF	0.476	0.450	0.349	0.304	0.050	0.078
PsyCap		-0.215		-0.325		0.351
R^2	0.041	0.041	0.017	0.095	0.010	0.113

Table 4. Dataset of hierarchical analysis for the trial-role conflict (FIW)

Variable	Job burnout					
	Emotional exhaustion		Cynicism		Professional Efficacy	
	First step	Second step	First step	Second step	First step	Second step
Gender	0.017	0.001	-0.032	-0.015	0.115	-0.102
Age	-0.059	-0.044	-0.092	-0.026	0.034	-0.023
Teaching experience	-0.107	-0.109	-0.059	-0.047	0.041	0.027
Marital status	0.141	0.111	0.020	-0.023	0.004	0.041
FIW	0.213	0.167	0.350	0.310	-0.203	-0.158
PsyCap		-0.216		-0.296		0.313
R^2	0.040	0.044	0.016	0.120	0.010	0.093

The role of Academic PsyCap, trial-role conflict, and burnout dimension (Cynicism)

The study found that trial-role conflict (WIF and FIW), as indicated in Tables 3 and 4, positively correlated with job burnout, particularly cynicism. On the other hand, academic PsyCap negatively correlated with job burnout and cynicism. Academic PsyCap exhibited a partially moderating effect of WIF, FIW, and cynicism, as the regression coefficient for FIW reduced when PsyCap was included. For WIF, the coefficient decreased from 0.349 to 0.304 (Table 3), while for FIW, the coefficient decreased from 0.350 to 0.310 (Table 4).

The role of Academic PsyCap in trial-role conflict and burnout dimension (professional efficacy)

The trial-role conflict subscales, WIF and FIW, exhibit distinct associations with professional efficacy. WIF demonstrates a positive correlation (0.060) with professional efficacy, while FIW shows a negative correlation (0.060). Similarly, the correlation between academic Psychological Capital (PsyCap) and professional Efficacy exhibits variability. PsyCap positively correlated with professional efficacy, specifically regarding work-family (WIF) and family-work relationships (FIW). PsyCap did not act as an intermediary between work-family (WIF) and professional efficacy variables. The incorporation of PsyCap in the analysis did not lead to a reduction in the regression coefficient for WIF. PsyCap partially moderated the link between FIW (work-family interface) and professional efficacy. Integrating PsyCap into the study led to a reduction in the size of the regression coefficient for FIW.

Correlation between trial-role and job burnout: Teacher perspectives

The results of statistical analysis indicate a strong correlation between trial-role conflict and job burnout, including emotional exhaustion, cynicism, and teacher efficacy. To sharpen this finding, we selected six teachers with characteristics ranging from gender to teaching experience to academic rank. Table 5 displays the interview data for the selected subjects.

Table 5. Subject characteristic for interview

No	Initial	Gender	Teaching experience	Academic rank
1	LI	Male	17 years	Associate professor
2	YM	Female	15 years	Associate professor
3	YL	Male	11 years	Associate professor
4	DE	Female	7,5 years	Assistant professor
5	YT	Female	4,5 years	Assistant professor
6	NI	Male	Three years	Lecturer

Then, based on teaching experience, the author divided the subjects into two groups: the senior group with more than ten years of teaching experience and the beginner group with less than ten years of experience.

A group of senior teachers with more than ten years of teaching experience

The author expected a group of experienced teachers to have perceptive and diverse perspectives on job burnout and the struggle between professional obligations, medical duties, and familial commitments. The excerpts below represent the results of the interviews:

With a high teaching load, clinical practice of nurses in hospitals, and family obligations, nursing teachers must maintain a harmonious balance between these three complex roles (LI).

Creating an organized schedule, determining priorities, and coordinating with colleagues and family members are very important. These steps are very helpful in managing the difficulties that arise from the complexity of the nursing role (YM).

The following part describes senior nursing teachers' perspectives towards their juniors: The senior teachers asserted that they often came to the meeting without enough preparation, and they relied much on us to teach them clinical procedures that they actually could learn from articles or Google (LI).

I frequently observe new teachers arriving with enthusiasm and innovative ideas, but sadly, this enthusiasm frequently falls short of the requisite practical knowledge and experience (YM).

Group of novice teachers with less than ten years of teaching experience.

Novice teachers may confront major challenges such as job burnout and trial-role conflict. Juggling the responsibilities of teaching, clinical practice, and family obligations while striving to establish oneself in the field can result in overwhelmed, stressed, and fatigued emotions. Novice teachers often find themselves frightened by the responsibilities of various roles in education. The following is an interview with the participants:

The balance between my trial duty and other responsibilities has undeniably presented difficulties for my well-being and my ability to conduct my job effectively... I have to address this issue through self-discipline to make me feel comfortable and mitigate my burnout (DE)

In an effort to mitigate burnout and emotional feelings caused by the complexity of the role of a nursing teacher, I try to set clear boundaries between professional and personal tasks and prioritize self-discipline. Sometimes, I also discuss with colleagues to reduce the emotions that arise (YT)

Discussion

A Positive relationship between trial-role Conflict and job Burnout

Among China's nursing college teachers, the findings demonstrated a positive association between trial-role conflict, work-family (WIF), and exhaustion as emotional feeling, as well as between family-work (FIW) and cynicism. These results corroborated earlier findings (Erdamar & Demirel, 2014). Erdamar and Demirel (2014) confirm that working conditions significantly impact work-family conflict in all seven countries. The primary factor that causes the greatest detrimental effect on work and family roles is the level of job pressure in terms of intensity and the number of hours required. The influence of family characteristics on work-family issues is not significantly found, but it provides greater opportunities in caregiving and household relationships. One of the reasons for this negative correlation is that individuals frequently face enduring stress and feel overwhelmed when confronted with an excessive administrative workload, high expectations, and limited resources.

The findings of this present study are quite similar to the previous research conducted by Erdamar and Demirel (2014). They found a positive correlation between teachers' work-family and family-work conflicts. Their findings revealed that work-family roles had a stronger impact than family-work relationship issues, which cause job dissatisfaction, stress, and organisational commitment issues. These problems also affect family life at home. Teachers often discussed work problems with their families, resulting in more conflicts at home due to job requirements. Teachers frequently report experiencing physical and mental fatigue, stress, and nervousness at home as a result of work-related issues. Meanwhile, WIF and FIW positively correlate to emotional cynicism and exhaustion, but they differ regarding the elements of teacher professional efficacy. WIF positively influenced professional efficacy, but FIW had a negative impact (Edinger & Edinger, 2018).

Academic Psychological Capital (PsyCap) is a mediating role between trial-role and job burnout.

The finding that Academic Psychological Capital (PsyCap) is a mediating variable in the relationship between trial-role conflict and job burnout, particularly the dimensions of emotional feeling such as exhaustion and cynicism, is deemed as consistent with previous research findings (Sarwar et al., 2021; Zewude & Hercz, 2021). Similarly, Sarwar et al. (2021) also reported that PsyCap elements showed a significant correlation to emotional exhaustion. The finding indicated that PsyCap becomes the key element in contributing to work-family conflict and the subsequent indicator of satisfaction as well as balance. This finding is different from a study by Toprak et al. (2022), who claimed that the psychological capital variable cannot become the mediating variable of the correlation between work-family and job burnout categories. They also found that the work-family relationship contributes to the variable of job stress among nursing teachers. However, it can moderate the influence of WFC on job stress.

Another finding indicates that higher psychological elements may mitigate the negative impacts of work-family connections on teachers' job burnout by augmenting individuals' coping strategies, such as resilience and aptitude for handling their stress. The PsyCap variable does not provide its function as a mediating variable to verify the relationship between work-family and job burnout conflicts. The next part is academic PsyCap, which has four indicators: silence, self-efficacy, hope, and optimism, essential in mitigating the impact of trial and nursing teachers' job burnout. Nursing teachers with higher PsyCap elements are likelier to have lower emotional exhaustion (Zewude & Hercz, 2021).

Senior vs. Novice Nursing Teachers in the Relationship Between trial-role and Job Burnout

Quantitative findings reveal interesting findings: Senior nursing teachers with more than ten years of work experience have higher job burnout scores (emotional exhaustion 15.04 and cynicism 8.51) compared to novice nursing teachers with less than ten years of teaching experience (average score: emotional exhaustion was 12.83 and cynicism was 7.9). Interview results also corroborate this quantitative finding: The senior teaching group typically encounters more complex problems and perceives the complexity of their work as a challenge. In contrast to the novice teachers, they tend to consult with colleagues, including senior teachers, regarding the complexity of their role in their work. When balancing teaching duties, clinical practice tasks in health, and personal tasks, the group of novice teachers views the complexity of work as a challenge for learning (Yedidia et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2021).

Yenidia et al. (2014) reported that 4 out of 10 senior nursing educators face their emotional situation because they are dissatisfied with their administrative workload and inability to manage their time. Consequently, they often face emotional exhaustion and job stress. In addition to having higher emotional exhaustion, senior nursing teachers also have a higher cynicism than novice nursing teachers. It aligns with research by Kaminski-Ozturk & Reid (2024), indicating that senior teachers perceive themselves as mentors, given the perception of novice teachers as low-quality and prone to undervaluation.

Conclusion

This study made a significant scientific contribution to nursing education. First, there is a positive relationship between trial-role conflict (teaching, clinical practice, and family) and the dimensions of job burnout, especially teacher exhaustion and cynicism. Second, a negative relationship exists between one of the trial-role conflicts, family interfering with work (FIW), and the third dimension of job burnout, professional efficacy. Both of these findings provide opportunities for nursing faculty to make policies that support the flexibility of teachers' work. The findings of this inquiry could provide implications for nursing policies and practices in different Asians facing burnout, potentially refining the quality of job satisfaction and retention among nursing teachers.

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